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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Stratospheric balloons offer near space observing conditions for a small fraction of the cost of an equivalent satellite. Balloon telescopes can make cutting-edge astrophysical observations, while also providing a platform to advance the technology readiness level of key systems for future space missions. Furthermore, balloon astronomy offers outstanding training opportunities. Typical experiment timeframes allow graduate students to play a key role in the instrument design, field campaigns, and scientific data analysis. In this white paper we will overview Canadian involvement in balloon astrophysics and outline the priorities of the balloon astronomy community for the coming decade. These priorities are: continued stable funding for the development of balloon-borne experiments, competitions for larger funding awards that would support the building of balloon-borne observatories or equivalent particle astrophysics experiments, support for PIs to access existing pointing platforms and balloon gondola technology, and opportunities for long duration conventional balloon and super-pressure balloon flights.

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1 Introduction

Stratospheric helium balloons can lift science payloads of $>2,500$ kg to altitudes of up to 45 km above the Earth's surface. As these heights place science payloads above more than 99% of atmospheric column, stratospheric ballooning offers an opportunity for astrophysicists to build experiments and telescopes that operate in near-space conditions for at about 1% of the cost of an equivalent satellite.

Balloon telescopes have several important advantages compared to ground-based telescopes. They provide access to regions of the electromagnetic spectrum that are not accessible from the ground such as the ultraviolet, high energy X-rays and gamma rays, and the far-IR, that would otherwise require an expensive satellite telescope. Balloon telescopes can also be built, launch and return data on a ~ 5 year period, which makes them well suited for training graduate students in for careers in space-astrophysics. Because of this short turnaround balloon telescopes can be used to test and NASA Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of new technology, an important prerequisite to incorporating the technology on future satellite missions.

However there are also some disadvantages of balloon astronomy. Balloon telescopes have mass and size limitations, and sophisticated motor control and position tracking systems are usually required to point a suspended telescope. Balloon launches often require waiting for appropriate weather. Also conventional scientific balloons are zero-pressure, that is they require the gas pressure inside the balloon to be the same as in the surrounding atmosphere. At night the gas inside the balloon cools and the balloon volume contracts, requiring drops of significant ballast mass to push the balloon back up to the target altitude. In practice this limits flights to a few days in locations where the sun sets, though longer flights are possible in regions where the sun does not set like Kiruna, Sweden or McMurdo Station, Antarctica.

In the past 10 years balloon astronomy has benefited from improvements in motor controller technology, digital electronics, carbon fiber gondola construction, new detectors, and higher bandwidth telemetry systems. The next decade shows even more promise with NASA's development of super-pressure balloons, which can be operate at a higher pressure than the surrounding atmosphere. Super-pressure balloons will be able to make making several month flights from mid-latitude locations, and will be able to keep a steady altitude profile even in locations where there the sun sets. With this new ballooning technology it is now possible to build and construct balloon-borne observatories, which in addition to training students and testing technology, provide significant legacy datasets to the astronomy community.

2 Progress in Canadian Involvement in Balloon Astronomy over the Past Decade

Over the past decade Canadian astronomers have played an important role in many key balloon-astronomy experiments.

- **The Balloon-Borne Large Aperture Sub-mm Telescope for Polarimetry (BLASTPol)** was a NASA funded balloon-borne polarimeter which mapped linear polarization simultaneously at 250, 350, and 500 μm . The readout, attitude control, and pointing systems in addition to the payload control software were all designed and built by Barth Netterfield's research group at the University of Toronto. BLASTPol measured linearly polarized radiation from dust grains aligned with their local magnetic field, and used these observations to map out magnetic fields in star forming regions. BLASTPol launched in 2010 and 2012, both times from Antarctica. In the second Antarctic flight BLASTPol made a deep ~ 50 hour map of the young Vela C molecular cloud, which is the most detailed magnetic field map to date of a massive star forming region. BLASTPol has placed constraints on the two-grain model of interstellar dust (Gandilo et al., 2016), and has been used to show that magnetic fields influence the structure of molecular clouds over many density scales (Soler et al., 2017; Fissel et al., 2019).
- **The E and B Experiment (EBEX)** was a NASA funded CMB polarization mapping experiment operating in frequency bands at 150, 250 and 410 GHz (EBEX Collaboration et al., 2018). EBEX had two flights: an engineering flight from Ft. Sumner, NM in June 2009 and a flight from the NASA Long Duration Balloon (LDB) facility in McMurdo Station, Antarctica in January 2013. EBEX was the first balloon-borne telescope to operate large TES detector arrays in the stratosphere, and Matt Dobbs' group at McGill University played a key role by designing and building the Digital Frequency Domain Multiplexer readout system for the detector arrays.
- **Spider:** Spider is a mm-polarimeter, with three bands measuring linearly polarized radiation at 90 and 150 GHz (Gualtieri et al., 2018). Spider is primarily designed to make extremely sensitive, high-fidelity maps of the Cosmic Microwave Background, particularly on large angular scales. As such the telescope was designed to minimize systematic effects, for example by incorporating an easily characterized lens system instead of a larger reflective optics system. The large beam sizes (30' and 42' beam FWHM) allows on the ground far-field telescope beam characterization. The telescope was built by an international collaboration, including funding from both NASA and the Canadian Space Agency. UBC and Toronto developed the detector readout electronics and balloon-gondola/software systems, respectively. The first Spider launch took place from the NASA long duration balloon facility at McMurdo Station, Antarctica in January 2015. A second Antarctic flight including a 285 GHz band for characterization of polarized dust foregrounds is scheduled for December 2020.
- **The Super pressure Balloon-borne Imaging Telescope (SuperBIT)** is a 0.5m, wide-field diffraction limited (0.25'') telescope. The gondola and pointing system developed for SuperBIT provides 0.7'' telescope pointing stability with 0.05'' focal plane stability over a 0.5° field-of-view, over the course of a 5 minute exposure (Romualdez et al., 2016). SuperBIT observes in 7 bands from the near-IR to the near UV. SuperBIT is designed to fly on a mid-latitude super-pressure balloon for up to 100 days. The project, funded in Canada by FAST, is led by the University of Toronto, where the key enabling technology has been developed. It's primary science goal is to use weak and strong lensing around 150 galaxy clusters to determine their mass, and calibrate other galaxy cluster mass determination techniques. The instrument has been fully qualified over several engineering flights, and is awaiting the next flight opportunity on NASA's super pressure balloon platform.
- **High Contrast Imaging Balloon System (HiCIBaS)** is a Canadian-led payload funded by the CSA's FAST program to develop and demonstrate the performance of high contrast imaging hardware on a stratospheric balloon flight (Allain et al., 2018; Côté et al., 2018). The work is primarily lead by five graduate students, with supervision from Prof. Simon Thibault. The payload had their first launch from Timmins as part of the CSA's STRATOS program in August 2018.

- **The next-generation BLAST Polarimeter (BLAST-TNG):** BLAST-TNG is an international collaboration that has built a sub-mm balloon borne polarimeter, led by the University of Pennsylvania, that will map dust polarization to study magnetic fields in nearby molecular clouds, diffuse gas clouds in the interstellar medium, and in nearby galaxies. New optics give BLAST-TNG a best resolution of $30''$ ($5\times$ better than BLASTPol), while large detectors arrays will result in a $>10\times$ mapping speed increase, making BLAST-TNG the most sensitive single dish polarimeter ever built (Galitzki et al., 2014; Lourie et al., 2018). BLAST-TNG is scheduled for a first flight from McMurdo Station, Antarctica in December 2019. BLAST-TNG has significant Canadian involvement from astrophysicists at Queen’s University and the University of Toronto.
- **The High Energy Light Isotope eXperiment (HELIX)** is a particle spectrometer that will measure the relative levels of the Be^9 and Be^9 isotopes in cosmic rays incident to the Earth. HELIX will provide important data for understanding the properties of cosmic rays in our local galactic environment. The instrument is scheduled for a first NASA flight during the December 2020 from McMurdo Station, Antarctica. HELIX with significant involvement from David Hanna’s group at McGill University.

3 Current Funding Mechanisms and Flight Opportunities for Balloon Astronomy in Canada

3.1 Funding

Since 2011 funding for stratospheric balloon borne payloads has been provided by the Canadian Space Agency’s (CSA) Flights and Fieldwork for the Advancement of Science and Technology (FAST) program. In total there have been five completed calls for proposals, with 72 projects awarded a combined total of 21 Million Canadian dollars. A sixth call for proposals has been announced in 2019 with a closing date of October 18th. However, this program (and these totals) also covers rocket payloads, nano-satellites/cubesats, space-analog environments, laboratory work, rover simulation environments, and aircraft, in all fields, including atmospheric physics, space sciences, space technology, space health/life sciences, planetary exploration, and solar physics as well as astrophysics. Only a fraction of the total funds have been available for astrophysics balloon experiments.

For payloads involving a launch within the period covered by the award the maximum total funding available over the course of a three year award has ranged from 250,000 CAD to 500,000 CAD. Of this funding, a significant fraction of the award is meant to be devoted to training highly qualified personnel (HQP), including undergraduate and graduate students, postdoctoral fellows, and other trainees. Multiple Canadian institutions may apply to FAST for the same project as long as the individual roles are clearly defined. Even so, this level of funding is adequate for a Canadian contribution to a multinational collaboration, but is inadequate for an all-Canadian project.

3.2 Flight opportunities

The CSA’s Stratospheric Balloon program (STRATOS) has provided launch opportunities to over 24 Canadian scientific balloon payloads since its beginning in 2012. Balloon launch support is provided by the Centre national d’études spatiales (CNES) of France, through a cooperation agreement with the CSA. Most of the launches CNES has provided took off from the airport in Timmins, Ontario. However there have also been STRATOS launches from Alice Springs, Australia (2017) and Kiruna, Sweden (2016). The time in the stratosphere for these flights has ranged from 10 hours to several days.

For projects with NASA funded U.S. collaborators, flights are also available through NASA’s Columbia Scientific Balloon Facility (CSBF) from a variety of locations, including long duration (weeks long) flights from Antarctica. However, these opportunities are only available to NASA funded U.S. projects.

4 Priorities for the Canadian Balloon Astronomy Community in the Next Decade

1. **Continued support for HQP training and technology development:** CSA FAST support has allowed

Canadian astronomers to participate and play significant leadership roles in many balloon astrophysics experiments. In particular the CSA FAST program has allowed many graduate students, undergraduate students and HQP to be trained in experiment design, construction, and scientific analyzing data. We believe strongly that the CSA should continue to support the FAST program.

2. **Access to super-pressure and long duration balloon-borne flights:** Short 1-2 day flights are important for testing technology and proving that experiments work. However, long duration balloon flights offer the opportunity for balloon telescopes to undertake significant astrophysical surveys that will have important results and provide legacy datasets to the astronomy community. We recommend that the Canadian astronomy community look into options for obtaining long duration balloon launches, and super-pressure flights for Canadian led experiments. One option is for the CSA to also contract with NASA to provide long duration flights. NASA is in the process of developing super-pressure balloon platforms, which are overpressured compared to the local atmosphere and therefore can keep a nearly uniform volume even when the balloon cools. Super-pressure balloons can lift up to ~ 1200 kg payloads to altitudes of 30 to 40km for 70-100 days and can launch from mid-latitude locations. These capabilities are still in development, however two super-pressure experiments have already successfully launched and flown from Wanaka, NZ, and widespread use of these super-pressure balloons is expected in the next few years. Access to mid-latitude super-pressure balloon telescopes would allow Canadian astronomers build balloon-borne observatories that could take months of scientific data instead of days, operate in wavelength regimes that require dark skies, and view more of the sky.

3. **Competitions to fund Canadian led large experiments:** At present funding required for a large-scale balloon telescope is not available to Canadian PIs. The cap for funding from the CSA's FAST program is limited to at most 500,000 CAD, spread over 3 years. While this funding level is enough to secure Canadian participation in an already existing international collaboration on a balloon astrophysics project it is realistically not sufficient to build a state of the art balloon telescope. For comparison NASA's Astrophysics Research and Analysis Program (APRA) for sub-orbital experiments awarded on average the equivalent of between 350,000 CAD to 660,000 per year for up to 5 years of funding, between fiscal year 2014-2018 (NASA APRA Solicitation APR 2018).

We suggest that CSA should develop a funding call, open to Canadian led end-to-end missions that would provide funding for Canadian PIs to develop and lead balloon-borne astrophysics payloads. This funding should be for 5 years, should include the provision of a long duration balloon flight opportunity, and should not preclude applying for matching funding from the CFI Innovation fund. In return for this increased funding level, the applying teams should have to demonstrate important science returns to Canadian astronomy community, plans for training HQP in space astrophysics, and support for the mission from the Canadian astronomy community. This could be run as a new category in FAST, or as a new program.

4. **Balloon gondola and flight infrastructure support:** There are significant complexities in the development of a balloon-borne telescope that are common between all or most instruments, including pointed gondolas, power systems, thermal control, and safety analysis, and associated ground station and flight software. Canadian astronomy would benefit from access to and support for these systems. Such a proposal has similarities to the Wallops Arc Second Pointer (e.g. Kislat et al. 2017,) developed by NASA (but WASP only includes the pointing system, not the full gondola and associated elements), and the CNES developed gondola used by PILOT (Bernard et al., 2016) and FIREBALL (Montel et al., 2016). This would decrease the expertise required for Canadian instrumentalists to build balloon-astronomy payloads, and would greatly increase the chance of mission success by eliminating the risk of designing and deploying a completely new telescope support system. The expertise and technology required for such a system has been developed in Canada (e.g. BLAST: Pascale et al. 2008, SuperBIT: Romualdez et al. 2016 and Spider: Shariff et al. 2014). The system and support could additionally be exported to support internationally funded experiments - potentially as an avenue to provide access to NASA super-pressure and LDB balloon flights.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Stratospheric balloons offer a rapid option to near space-quality observing conditions, for a small fraction of the cost of an equivalent satellite. Access to super-pressure balloon flights will allow for longer science campaigns of 2-3 months from mid-latitude locations. This will make balloon telescopes practical that require dark sky conditions, such as optical telescopes for large weak-lensing surveys and for characterizing exoplanets. Even for telescopes that do not require dark conditions in the far-IR/sub-mm access to long duration mid-latitude flights would make it possible to map almost anywhere in the sky, compared the $\sim 15\%$ accessible during Antarctic daytime flights. With increase visibility far-IR and sub-mm balloon borne telescopes could study the ISM, magnetic fields and star formation in the Galactic Centre, in nearby galaxies like the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds, and in all of the nearby star forming regions, and determine how the regulation of star formation changes with environment.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

There are additional risks associated with balloon astronomy that are not applicable to ground based telescopes, such as landing in a location where the payload is severely damaged or recovery is difficult (such as a body of water or mountain range), loss of launch opportunities due to poor weather or telescope systems breaking or overheating due to the harsh environment in the stratosphere where these experiments operate. These risks can be mitigated by making telescope systems easily replaceable with redundancies and fall back systems in place, using common systems and subsystems between projects, and by sending large quantities of science data through telemetry systems, so that the recovery of the payload is not absolutely required to obtain the experiment science data. The NASA super-pressure balloon-program still requires additional testing, and will probably not be available for balloon-flights for another 2-3 years.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canadians already play important leadership roles in the design of balloon gondolas, detector readout and data acquisition electronic systems, quick look software, and fine pointing control. However, increases in funding for specially selected large projects and access to flights longer than a few days would give Canadian scientists the opportunity to develop and lead balloon astrophysics missions.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

There are a number of research groups in Canada who are involved in balloon astronomy and have an interest in seeing this program grow. Canadian scientists will have access to the data generated from experiments like BLAST-TNG, which will be made publicly available for future research in star formation and galactic structure studies.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Balloon telescopes can be used to test technology in a near space environment and to train highly qualified

personnel. This will benefit future satellite missions such as CASTOR, SPICA, and the Origins Space Telescope.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Large balloon telescopes typically cost of order ~ 5 million dollars to design, build and deploy, which is a factor of ~ 100 less than the cost of an equivalent space telescope. Though the flights are shorter than for a typical satellite telescope, scientific balloons allow astronomers to build telescopes that cannot be done from the ground. Balloons also allow testing of technologies for use in future space missions. With longer flights (70 to 100 days) that can be provided by super-pressure balloon flights the “cost per photon” will further decrease for balloon telescopes. The faster cadence, and lower costs allow balloon experiments to use state-of-the-art detectors and other technologies, further increasing their value.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

Balloon telescopes inherently have a higher degree of per-mission risk than satellite missions, since part of their goals are to test new technology, and since the launch vehicle is less reliable. Since balloon launches are subject to the uncertainty of weather, launches can be delayed, occasionally by up to a year, causing schedule and budget risks. However, these risks can be balanced against the lower payload costs, and the high likelihood of being able to improve and re-fly payloads multiple times.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

Balloon telescopes are an excellent way of training HQP in instrument design, aerospace research, and project management. The need to design and build large and complicated systems quickly often entails partnerships with industry. Finally balloon telescopes, which operate at the boundary terrestrial and space environment, offer a way to captivate the imagination of students and the public. For students, balloons can provide an entry into space research, both by working as a part of teams building telescopes and also by designing their own small balloon-borne experiments.

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